

Mixed Stochasticity and Determinism in Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 21, 2024

Quantum mechanics is often called a stochastic theory, but we argue that it seems to be a mixture of stochasticity and determinism. We trace this to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which arises in what seems to be a solely deterministic theory of special relativity. In particular, E and p are sharp values and p cannot exist without v , which itself seems to be a deterministic value at first glance (but is probably more of an average). We argue that $-Et+px$ has degeneracies for $t=t_0 + n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$, where n is an integer. At the same time the repetition of crests/troughs in $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle wavefunction (unusual probability) is deterministic, but within a crest or trough there is probability linked to position. Furthermore, even though $p \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$ and $pp \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$ give deterministic values for all x , the unnormalized $p\{\cos(px)+i \sin(px)\}$ and $pp\{\cos(px) +i \sin(px)\}$ are not and differ for p and $-p$, something which does not occur for p or $-p$ in pp .

If one considers a bound single particle quantum state, further stochasticity appear through $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$. There is now added stochasticity through the $a(p)$'s, but determinism because $KE_{\text{ave}} = -1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W$ must equal $E-V(x)$ at each x point.

We note that $\exp(ipx)$ does not contain time and represents a probability pattern throughout space, but nevertheless one that is restricted to a direction (positive x direction) and associated with a deterministic average velocity. Given that $V(x)$ cannot distinguish kinetic energy for p or $-p$ classically, (both have $pp/2m$), then given that $pp/2m(\cos(px)+i\sin(px))$ and $pp/2m(\cos(-px) + i \sin(-px))$ are not the same, one must combine these two probabilities if one wishes to use $V(x)$ in an equation.

We argue that for a quantum bound state at low energy levels, one sees crests and troughs. Each crest/trough represents somewhat stochastic behaviour, but the progression of different crests and troughs is linked with determinism. If the crests become very narrow, we argue that the stochasticity is becoming less important because these \hbar/p regions probably cannot be resolved. Furthermore, we argue that narrow crests means no contribution from low p values associated with wide wavelengths \hbar/p . Furthermore, there is no reason to have high p values either because these cause problems with the average kinetic energy value at x . Thus, as the stochasticity diminishes as energy levels increase and crests decrease, one arrives at the point at which a single crest is essentially linked with a single p and there is determinism due to the numerous tiny wavelength crests.

Mixed Stochasticity and Determinism Due to Special Relativity

We have argued in previous notes that stochasticity in quantum mechanics arises from what seems to be a purely deterministic theory- special relativity. Special relativity is based on sharp E and p values as well as sharp x,t and velocity values. At first glance, there seems to be no uncertainty or probability unless one examines the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et+px \quad ((1))$$

A is degenerate for: $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ and $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ ((2))

This degeneracy suggests an uncertainty region or resolution region of \hbar/E in time and \hbar/p in space for a constant p . In other words, there is probability behaviour, but also deterministic repeated \hbar/E and \hbar/p regions described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Thus, a mixture of stochasticity and determinism exists, we argue.

At first one may suggest that p and $p^2/2m$ hold at every x point for $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. there is complete determinism. This follows from:

$$P_{ave} = p \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad p^2/2m_{ave} = p^2/2m \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

These, however, are average values at each x point because the unnormalized averages are not constant, i.e.:

$$P_{ave} \text{ unnormalized} = p (\cos(px) + i\sin(px)) \quad \text{and} \quad p^2/2m_{ave} \text{ unnormalized} = p^2/2m (\cos(px) + i\sin(px)) \quad ((4))$$

From ((4)), one sees that unnormalized $p^2/2m$ differs for p and $-p$, whereas $p^2/2m$ does not. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a directional probability and this has consequences for p and $p^2/2m$ averages as will be seen in the quantum single particle bound state.

Single Particle Quantum Bound State

In the case of a single particle classical bound state, one considers $v(x)$, $x(t)$ at each point and assigns a force $F(x)$ (usually no t appears in the argument) at each x to describe the change in v . This is the deterministic approach.

If one has $\exp(ipx)$, this represents a static probability scheme throughout all of space, with stochasticity in the crests and troughs of $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$, but determinism through velocity and the repeated crests/troughs. Given the crests or resolution regions, it is impossible to describe the situation deterministically.

If, however, one wishes to use $V(x)$, the classical potential, then one is forced to impose a deterministic average constraint of a constant E at each x point. This suggests a partially stochastic recipe of:

$$W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{such that}$$

$$\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((6))$$

We note that $V(x)$ is energy and so $p^2/2m$ is the same for $-p$ and p . In quantum mechanics, however, the unnormalized average $p^2/2m$ is direction dependent. Thus, one must include both p and $-p$ in the somewhat stochastic equation ((6)).

One finds that $W(x)$ also has crests/troughs which represent stochasticity (but also some determinism) as kinetic energy (average) changes. The repeated crests/troughs have different heights and base widths and so there is also determinism here.

High Energy Situation

If the energy level is increased, one notices that crest/trough base widths shrink. This suggests that $a(p)$ values for $p < p_0$ approach 0. If one requires a certain average KE at each x , then one cannot include p values $> p_0$ and so one essentially has a very narrow range of p values in each \hbar/p narrow region. In other words, stochasticity is diminishing and determinism is taking over, i.e. one has the classical regime.

In such a case, there is a second solution for which the quantum approach has the same average KE for p and $-p$ namely a single p at each dx , i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Then, $\frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{\exp(ipx)}{\exp(ipx)} = \frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{\exp(-ipx)}{\exp(-ipx)}$. One no longer needs to add the two in $W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics follows from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ (for a free particle) and so contains both deterministic and stochastic features. The stochastic features are linked with $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ which follows from the degeneracy of $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$, while at the same time $n=\text{integer}$ suggests a repetition or determinism as does velocity which seems to be an average value.

If one considers a bound system and brings in $V(x)$ classical, one cannot have changes in tiny dx because of $\hbar/p > dx$. Thus, a new stochasticity, $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ appears, but there is determinism as well because $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} = E-V(x)$. $W(x)$ displays crests and troughs indicating stochasticity, but there is also determinism due to $KE(\text{ave})$ within a crest and the series of crest heights, base widths etc.

As the crest base widths become smaller and smaller, we argue that the stochasticity becomes less and less prominent and one approaches a predominantly deterministic theory, especially if there is on way to resolve what happens within a tiny \hbar/p , i.e. now $dx > \hbar/p$.

References

- 1, Pomeau, Y. and Le Berre, M. Quantum mechanics as a statistical theory: a short history and worked example 2018 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.02884>